

A short comment on the criticism of Bhattacharya's Equation by R. C. Srivastava et. al.*

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In formulating any equation correlating two or more physical quantities, the dimensions should be balanced and the constants should be interpreted. This has been done in Bhattacharya's equation and its merits have been tested by many workers. Since R. C. Srivastava *et al.*, have referred to some interesting remarks it is deemed necessary to release a critical assessment of the merits of both the equations, as follows :

1. The critical stability concentration, a , when coagulation time, t , is infinitely large, follows from both equations. Putting Bhattacharya's equation in the form,

$$C-a = \frac{m \cdot \frac{1}{t}}{n + \frac{1}{t}}$$

when $t = \infty$, $C-a = 0$ or $C = a$, which means that the sol will coagulate in indefinitely long time upto the concentration, a , of the electrolyte; which is, therefore, the critical stability concentration of the electrolyte for the sol. In Srivastava-Abrol equation²,

$$t = \frac{K}{C(C-a)},$$

when $t = \infty$, either $C = 0$, or $C-a = 0$. Since ' C ' cannot be zero, therefore $C-a = 0$ or $C = a$, which has the same meaning as given above. The fact, however, remains that $C = 0$ in a coagulation process by adding an electrolyte has no physical significance which has been stressed by the authors under reference to claim the absurdity of a negative value of t from Bhattacharya's equation.

2. In the phenomenon of rapid coagulation $t = 0$. Putting Bhattacharya's equation in the form $C-a = \frac{m}{n \frac{1}{t} + 1}$, $C-a = m$, when t is put equal to zero. Therefore, the effective concentration of the electrolyte for rapid coagulation is m which is equivalent to $C-a$, where C is the total concentration of the electrolyte added. On the contrary, if we put $t = 0$ in Srivastava-Abrol equation, $t = \frac{k}{C(C-a)}$, we get $C(C-a) = \infty$, assuming k is a finite quantity. Obviously, this result is untenable as the concentration, C , cannot be an infinite

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1. R. P. Srivastava and I. P. Abrol, *Kolloid. Z., and Z. fur Polymere*, 1967, **218**, 62.

2. R. P. Srivastava and I. P. Abrol, *Kolloid Z.U. Z. Polymere*, 1968, **222**, 61.

quantity. Hence, there is no solution of this equation, for rapid coagulation which is directly solved by Bhattacharya's equation.

3. In Bhattacharya's equation,

$$n = \frac{1}{t} \left[\frac{m-(C-a)}{(C-a)} \right]$$

Now, if $n = \frac{1}{t}$, $\frac{m-(C-a)}{(C-a)} = 1$ or $C-a = \frac{m}{2}$. Therefore, n is the reciprocal of the time of coagulation, t , when the amount of electrolyte added is half of m (the concentration at which the sol coagulates instantaneously). If t is larger by adding the concentration $\frac{m}{2}$ of an electrolyte, the sol is less susceptible and *vice versa*. Hence, n has been defined as the susceptibility factor of the sol to the electrolyte added, and it is a characteristic property of sols related to their stability. In the Smoluchowski's equation ϵ is the factor for slow coagulation which represents the effective number of collisions which depends on the nature of the electrolyte and stage of coagulation at time t , according to the degree of susceptibility of the sol. Hence it may be visualised that n of Bhattacharya's equation, which depends upon several stability factors, is related to ϵ of Smoluchowski also. Srivastava-Abrol's expression does not seem to afford any physical interpretation of the constant K .

4. The actual relation between C and $\frac{1}{t}$ in Bhattacharya's equation has been graphically shown to be nonlinear and it is generally asymptotic with the concentration axis at a small value of concentration, given by a . Therefore, the equation describes the behaviour of ' t ' for values greater than ' a ', which is actually the region of interest. For values, $C < a$, the equation, ipsofacto ceases to be applicable for determining t , but this has been the main argument of the authors under reference to show the absurdity of a negative value of t by putting $C = 0$. This is evidently meaningless and need not be pursued. For the region $C < a$, another equation for $t = \infty$ should be evolved to cover values less than $C = a$ to zero, which has not yet been possible.

5. It may further be noted that for slow coagulation of antimony sulphide sol with barium chloride, the linearity between $\frac{1}{t}$ and $C(C-a)$ has been shown in the paper under reference by joining only two points out of four. This is unwarranted.

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